

Capturing Elements of the Nature Futures Framework Through In Situ Place Descriptions: An Empirical Study in Urban Blue Locations

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Human-nature interaction is in constant flux, and capturing the present perceptions and imaginaries of urban nature could facilitate the development of scenarios that ensure positive futures for both nature and humans. This paper explores the feasibility of inferring and operationalizing the three key values of the Nature Futures Framework – Nature for Society, Nature as Culture, and Nature for Nature – through the language in place descriptions and place transformation suggestions, collected in situ in 57 urban blue spaces as part of a pilot citizen science project in the Netherlands. We suggest that cross-pollination between research working towards capturing place facets in natural discourse and the Nature Futures Framework has the potential to provide effective means for a better understanding and visualization of individual and collective nature-related values hold within communities in particular *places*, leading to transformations of urban nature in a way that is beneficial to both humans and nature.

Keywords: urban blue; urban nature; place descriptions; place transformations; Nature Futures Framework

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1 Introduction and Related Work

Geographical Information Science has made significant theoretical and methodological advances in the conceptualization, operationalization, extraction, and representation of platial information. One example is the body of work that has developed an advanced methodological toolkit to capture the richness of place facets through an in-depth analysis of *language* used to describe places. Relying on theories and analytic techniques from cognitive semantics, discourse and text analysis, this line of research leverages diverse types of place-related natural discourse – data collected through in situ free listing and surveys, but also through diverse geographical practices referred to as neogeography (Warf and Sui, 2010), encompassing passive (e.g., social media) and active (e.g., crowdsourcing) forms of Volunteered Geographic Information. This body of work provides valuable insights into a variety of aspects of human-environment relationships: wayfinding and navigation in natural settings, conceptualization of landscape features and the meaning of landscape terms across diverse linguistic and cultural communities, emotions evoked by certain places and activities and place appreciation more

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Table 1: Generic summary overview of the Nature Futures Framework (NFF) value perspectives (cf., Kramer et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2020, IPBES/TF/SCN/2021/1/2)

NFF perspective	Nature for Nature	Nature for Society	Nature as Culture
Summary description	In which nature has value in and of itself. Nature maintains its ability to function autonomously, and the preservation of nature's diversity and functions is of primary importance	In which nature is primarily valued, and sustainably managed for the benefit of humans	In which humans are perceived as an integral part of nature, where societies, cultures, traditions and faiths are intricately intertwined with nature, and relational values, such as those reflecting cultural identities and ways of life, are dominant
Prevailing value type	intrinsic values	relational values	instrumental values

generally, to name a few examples (Purves et al., 2023; Stock et al., 2019; Tenbrink, 2022; Tenbrink and Williams, 2022).

Linguistically informed analysis of place facets has advanced our understanding of the perception and use of cultural ecosystem services (CES), spanning across disciplines. The linguistic operationalization of CES, such as sense of place in the context of recreation, provides the first key step to the extraction and modelling of the perception and use of cultural ecosystem services across various spatial and temporal scales using verbal data (Egorova, 2021; Kim and Son, 2021; Langemeyer et al., 2023; Wartmann and Purves, 2018). In this paper, we build upon this line of work by exploring place descriptions of urban blue locations from the perspective of Nature Futures Framework values.

The Nature Futures Framework (NFF), proposed by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), is a tool for developing nature-positive scenarios (Pereira et al., 2020). Based on an in-depth analysis of a wide range of visions of positive futures for biodiversity and people, it embraces the diversity of human–nature relationships (Lundquist et al., 2021). As represented in Table 1, the NFF framework comprises three value perspectives that humans can hold towards nature: (1) Nature for Nature (NfN), (2) Nature for Society (NfS), and (3) Nature as Culture (NaC) (Durán et al., 2023; Lundquist et al., 2021). These three value perspectives encompass intrinsic (NfN), instrumental (NfS) and relational (NfC) values that people may hold towards nature. To date, the NFF has been successfully applied in dedicated sessions with stakeholders. Importantly, the NFF has been suggested as a tool to sketch futures and aid urban planning for green, sustainable cities that benefit the health of humans and nature alike (Mansur et al., 2022).

While ‘urban nature’, ‘urban blue and green’, and ‘natural environment’ are widely used terms, the conceptual distinctions often remain vague, and the terms appear to be used interchangeably. The classical view that separates and opposes natural and built environments has been contested as irrelevant given the context of the Anthropocene (Ahern, 2016). Hence, the term ‘urban nature’ emerged, generally referring to natural elements in cities, such as those found in urban blue and green spaces. There is also no clear distinction between urban green and blue spaces since the latter are often encountered amidst green spaces (Smith et al., 2021).

Humans benefit from the presence of urban nature in blue spaces, both in terms of how they experience urban settings (Herzog, 1989) as well as by the ecosystem services provided by nature, such as flood mitigation, food provisioning, and recreation (Keeler et al., 2019). Understanding the values humans give to urban nature in the context of local places and diverse populations that use them is essential for informing nature-positive scenarios by policy-makers. The current applications of the NFF (e.g., Kuiper et al., 2022) are unlikely to capture the full diversity of the population interacting with nature in the real world. Furthermore, they tend to capture broad visions of the future rather than ‘small-scale’ perceptions and transformation-related imaginaries in particular *places*.

Figure 1: The 57 urban blue locations visited during the *Water Rangers Twente* project in Almelo, the Netherlands

In this study we explore the feasibility of operationalizing and capturing the Nature Futures Framework elements through language in place descriptions in the context of urban nature in urban blue spaces, while simultaneously taking the first steps towards bridging between the two research communities. Research and policy working with the NFF could benefit from the *operationalization of its key constructs through language*, allowing for the leveraging of data collected across various spatial and temporal scales and including views from more diverse sources such as indigenous and local populations (Lahoti et al., 2023). Simultaneously, the research community working on cataloguing the richness with which place is reflected in natural discourse could benefit from the cross-pollination with a future and transformation-oriented framework, and it could engage deeper with *nature-related values of people as a facet of urban nature places*. We explore the feasibility of capturing NFF values in the descriptions of places and suggested place transformations, collected in situ in urban blue places, by addressing the following questions: (1) Can we capture the NFF values through language in the descriptions of places, and in the descriptions of suggested transformations? (2) Can this type of data reveal the directionality of suggested place transformations and the underlying NFF values?

2 Data and Methods

The study uses data collected as part of the citizen science project *Water Rangers Twente*, which ran in the summer of 2022 in Almelo, a city in the Netherlands. The project was developed for the temporarily displaced youth from Ukraine and had several aims, ranging from the contribution to children's place-bonding to the collection of data on the youth perception of urban blue. Grounded in the concept of planetary health, the project focussed on water bodies. On the one hand, participants explored the health of water bodies (e.g., water transparency, and presence of water animals and plants) as part of the national project *Vang de Watermonsters*. On the other, participants investigated and recorded places' attractiveness for visitation. Seventeen children took part in the project, with an average age of 10.6 ($SD = 1.9$), 11 (64.7%) of them being female. Participants worked in four teams, exploring a total of 57 locations (Figures 1 and 2), filling in 223 individual protocols on place

Figure 2: Diversity of places visited during the *Water Rangers Twente* project

attractiveness. This study uses subsections of place attractiveness protocols that included the following instructions and open-ended questions: ‘Please describe this place in three words’, ‘What do you like about this place?’ (combined into one dataset for this study, henceforth referred to as ‘place descriptions’, with a total of 560 entries), ‘Which two things would you change?’ (henceforth referred to as ‘place transformations’, with a total of 279 entries). Information from individual protocols was entered into one spreadsheet and translated into English by the project community manager (a native speaker of Ukrainian) and the project PI (the last author in this paper, a native speaker of Russian).

To address RQ 1, we combined the two datasets and compiled a file with unique linguistic expressions in order to reduce the annotation workload. Four authors of this study individually annotated linguistic expressions according to the definitions of the three NFF value perspectives. An additional category ‘Other’ was introduced to capture concepts that did not belong to any of the NFF elements. A concept could be annotated by multiple categories. We further jointly explored and discussed the key categories of encountered concepts and cases of ambiguity, and developed a draft annotation scheme (the key categories of linguistic expressions and corresponding values are represented in Table 2). Using the said scheme we re-annotated all the data for further analysis. To address RQ 2, we combined data from annotated individual protocols per place (since each place was visited and described by four to five project participants), so that one place-related data entry represented three vectors corresponding to three value perspectives. We further calculated the fraction of each value perspective relative to the total number of value perspectives expressed for each place. For example, for three participants who provided descriptions of a place annotated by the following values ($NfS = 1$, $NfN = 5$, $NaC = 6$), we calculated the sum of all value perspectives represented ($S = 10$) and the individual contributions of each value perspective ($NfS = 1/10$, $NfN = 5/10$, $NaC = 6/10$). With the resulting values summing up to 1, we represent the relative fraction of each value perspective on (three axes) ternary plots. By doing so we correct for the variation in the number of linguistic expressions and values associated with different places. The procedure was conducted separately for two data subsets – place descriptions, and place transformations.

3 Results

RQ 1. Can we capture the NFF values through language in the descriptions of places, and in the descriptions of suggested transformations? Many linguistic expressions could be mapped onto one of the annotation categories in a relatively straightforward way: ‘Nature for Society’ (human-activities around nature, e.g., *swimming*, *fishing*; man-made objects that facilitate the experience of

Table 2: Examples of key categories of the annotation scheme used within this study. Note that place transformations are annotated according to the context, namely, the impact of adding or subtracting the element in a given category, i.e., whether it becomes more suitable for humans to obtain services from nature (Nature for Society; NfS), nature to flourish (Nature for Nature; NfN), or contributes to human-nature relations (Nature as Culture; NaC).

Category	Examples	NfS	NfN	NaC	Other
Human related activities	fishing, swimming, study, reading, recreate	✓			
Emotions, sentiments and quality assessments	beauty, nice, good, fine, aesthetics, motivating, cool, tranquil			✓	
Biota	ducks, flowers, flora, fauna, bees, plants, grass, flies		✓		
Biota related to food provisioning	berries, fish	✓	✓		
Natural objects and elements	lake, sand, field, water		✓		
Constructed objects relating to the experience of or control over nature	bench, built access to the water, bridge, dam, pontoon	✓			
Other constructed objects	house, monument, towers				✓
Sounds	noisy, loud				✓
Size and location-related descriptors	big, small, large, downtown				✓
Litter and pollution	litter, litter bins, polluted, dirty		✓	✓	

nature by humans, e.g., *ascent to the water, paths, benches for fishing*), ‘Nature for Culture’ (feelings and sentiments expressing relational value, e.g., *beautiful, serene, tranquil, happy, good, cool*), ‘Other’ (man-made objects without clear links to natural values, e.g., *house, statue, bridge*, various place facets not directly linked to any NFF values, e.g., *long, downtown*). The major case of ambiguity related to natural objects (e.g., *lake, field, sand, water*) and biota (*algae, duckweed, plants, thickets, toads, fleas, ducks*). While all four coders annotated such references as ‘Nature for Nature’ in place descriptions, there was a common agreement that such operationalization is simplistic: biota may, e.g., be mentioned for its benefits (*flowers*) or burden to humans (*nettles, bugs*) rather than its intrinsic value. The role of contextual information – even very primitive, in the form of verbs and adverbs such as *add/more* and *remove/less* – was clearly seen in the place transformations dataset, where expressions such as *add trees* and *more living creatures in the water* clearly represented the Nature for Nature values, while expressions such as *remove nettle* and *minus reeds* hint at the Nature for Society value perspective. Remarkably, the same concept could appear as both desirable and undesirable across protocols, revealing differences in individual perceptions; examples of such concepts include *duckweed, grass, water animals*. Other examples of contested concepts that can be reflective of multiple values are *litter* (one of the most frequent terms; can be interpreted as a nuisance to the experience of nature for humans, i.e., Nature for Culture, and also as a threat to nature itself, i.e., Nature for Nature), *berries* (another frequent term; related both to food provisioning, i.e., Nature for Society, but also to habitat for other species, i.e., Nature for Nature).

RQ 2. Can this type of data reveal the directionality of suggested place transformations and the underlying NFF values? Figure 3a illustrates the value perspectives captured in place descriptions of the 57 urban blue locations. While there are some reference to instrumental values (e.g., *one can swim*) and relational values (e.g., *tranquil, beautiful*), the average value perspective is skewed towards the intrinsic (Nature for Nature) value. This trend may represent the general cognitive salience of natural objects and biota in urban nature, and an their appreciation in the urban environment. However, it may partially also reflect the priming effect of the water quality measurement activity as well as the annotation bias addressed above (e.g., all references to biota annotated as Nature for Nature in place descriptions). Despite these possible biases, the diversity of places in terms of the NFF value perspectives is rather remarkable given the relatively small geographical area.

Figure 3: NFF values and transformation of urban blue places in Almelo, the Netherlands. (a) Ternary plot of the NFF value perspectives based on the merged annotations of place descriptions. Black dots represent individual places and the large green dot indicates the mean for all visited places. (b) Ternary plot of the NFF value perspectives based on the merged annotation of place descriptions and place transformation suggestions. Grey dots represent the initial position of places in respect to the NFF value perspectives (same as in Figure 3a), and blue dots represent the position of places in respect to the NFF value perspectives based on the merged annotation of place transformation suggestions. Individual places are connected with green lines. The large green arrow indicates the mean direction of the envisioned transformation, connecting the grey and blue circles representing the mean of initial value perspectives and the envisioned mean change to value perspectives respectively.

Figure 3b illustrates a visible shift towards the Nature for Society, instrumental value perspective. While we encounter a few suggestions that are primarily motivated by the intrinsic value (*add toads, more living creatures, clean, and fence the canal against people so that so that animals feel free without us*), the vast majority of transformation suggestions relate to improving places for human activities: arranging swimming access, reducing nuisance from litter, and creating more favorable conditions for fishing. For example, a site located near the stream Weezebeek (Figure 2, bottom right) falls close to the mean value characterization of across all annotated sites ($NfS = 0.16$, $NfN = 0.59$, $NaC = 0.25$) and its suggested transformation also falls close the the mean value perspective expressed ($NfS = 0.5$, $NfN = 0.25$, $NaC = 0.25$). The site was described by participants as *fine, good, and motivating* (NaC , relational value) but also had many words reflecting an intrinsic value perspective (NfN : *living creatures, transparency, snails, and few plants and few flowers*). The participants suggested adding *benches* and a *gazebo* and cleaning up *litter* reflecting a transformation of the site towards increasing some of its instrumental (NfS) aspects. Through a simple open-ended question on the desired change, we are thus effectively able to visualize the values and the desired futures in the context of the NFF.

4 Conclusion and Future Steps

The presented study is the first step towards capturing the NFF values in the descriptions of places and place transformations. While some of the concepts remain ambiguous without further contextual information, and while this type of data can be considered rather ‘thin’, it provides an initial insight into diverse local experiences and perceptions of nature and desired changes. As such, it can provide a window into the key concepts shaping communities’ mental models in relation to nature (Egorova et al., 2022; Jones et al., 2014), diverse frames of people–nature relations (Willemen et al., 2023), but also into the NFF value perspectives hold by communities in relation to certain urban nature localities, serving as a potential starting point for more focussed and engaged workshops that are currently leveraging

the NFF framework. Importantly, collection of such data today is facilitated not only by social media platforms, but also through the uptake of active crowdsourcing and citizen science, which increasingly engage disadvantaged, marginalized, and indigenous communities (Benyei et al., 2023; Moustard et al., 2021). In the context of citizen science projects with a strong educational element (both *Water Rangers Twente* and *Vang de Watermonsters* introduce participants to the core components of a healthy aquatic ecosystem), simple elicitation of suggested urban blue place transformations prior and following the project can also be used for assessing knowledge acquisition and the potential shift in values towards nature among project participants. In our future steps, we aim to develop and validate the annotation scheme for the NFF values based on the inter-rater reliability test, compile a more representative dataset, and prepare it as a training dataset for the machine learning identification of the NFF values in similar data. We also aim to explore how the three NFF values – intrinsic, instrumental, and relational – map and/or can be integrated with the primitive place facets – geographic, functional, emotive (Hamzei et al., 2020), leading to a more holistic representation of urban nature spots on the one hand, and linking nature futures scenarios to *places* on the other.

Author Contributions

E Egorova and S Teurlinx contributed the main idea and methodology. E Egorova and L Willemen contributed to the data collection. S Teurlinx, R van Halsema, ASM Deffner, and E Egorova contributed to the data annotation (RQ 1). S Teurlinx performed the data analysis (RQ 2). ASM Deffner and S Teurlinx prepared the figures. E Egorova and S Teurlinx contributed to the writing.

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